

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE DIGITAL SOCIETY.

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Abstract This article provides information about the role of women in all spheres of our country, in social spheres such as culture, science, public education, healthcare, sports, as well as in the digital society. It was noted that increasing the political, social and economic activity of women is one of the priorities of the state policy.

Key words: Science, education, ICT, women, electronic, digital, technology.

It is particularly noteworthy that the place and role of our women is increasing in the political life of our country, in state and community management, in all sectors of our economy, in social fields such as culture, science, public education, health care, and sports.

Today, a democratic state and a civil society are being established in Uzbekistan. Civil society requires women to protect their rights and interests and to have a natural desire to solve their problems. It is of great social importance for women and girls to be ready for this.

To increase the socio-political and social activity of women in our country, to create conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and industries, to ensure unconditional observance of their rights and legal interests, to protect motherhood and childhood Wide-scale work is being carried out to provide support, as well as to strengthen the institution of the family. Each period has its own development factor, need, demand and life principles. Naturally, their formation and development, giving them a special meaning,

during this period will be huge historical events that will determine the specific directions of the activity of the state, society, and socio-political institutions.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, one of the first steps in the protection of women's rights was recognition in Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "Women and men have equal rights." With this, the comprehensive participation of women in all spheres as an active member of the society in our country was legally guaranteed. Today, "Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020 is one of the important issues put forward in the Address to the Oliy Majlis on increasing the role and influence of women in the life of society, creating new opportunities for them", at the same time, on December 22, 2021 - in his speech at the 46th session of the United Nations Human Rights Council in February, he emphasized the issue of "resolutely continuing the work aimed at radically increasing the role of women in the social and political life of our country and in the business sector in terms of gender policy issues."

Uzbekistan's reforms are aimed at increasing the position of women in society, protecting their rights and opportunities as one of the priority values, while ensuring the primacy of human interests. In particular, increasing the political, social and economic activity of women is realized as one of the priorities of the state policy. Equal rights of men and women play an important role in people's well-being, social peace and economic stability. In this regard, the issue of ensuring women's employment, expanding opportunities for them to fully realize their aspirations and abilities is a constant focus of our state.

Today, digital knowledge and modern information technologies are one of the important conditions for progress. Digital technologies not only improve state and community management and create great convenience for people in the social sphere. It should be noted that the IT sector, computer operator-moderator, electronic auctions, trading branches, internet exchange, catalog of goods and services, electronic digital banks, electronic commerce, trading using mobile

phones, e-mails, electronic marketing, etc. We are witnessing the increasing active participation and influence of women and girls in the fields demanded by modern times and market relations, such as

According to UN data, today only 3% of the world's women study in educational institutions specialized in the field of information technologies. Among men, this figure is more than 10%. Women make up almost 50% of the workforce in the US, but only 25% in the ICT sector. In the last 5 years, thanks to the support of the world's technological sector and national governments, about 3500 events aimed at increasing the role of girls in the field of ICT and using information and communication technologies to ensure gender equality have been held. On September 14, 2017, the Global Coalition for Transforming Innovation was announced in New York under the auspices of the UN. In two years, the merger of 22 organizations and academic institutions ensured that women and girls took full advantage of the technological revolution. The coalition was supported by many world-famous companies and banks, including "Cisco", "Facebook", "JPMorgan Chase", "LinkedIn", "Sony". They decided to achieve gender equality in their fields of activity and use new technologies to advance this goal in all aspects.

Among them, a number of changes and developments can be observed in the field of ICT. In particular, the establishment of IT-parks and digital technology training centers in various regions of our republic serves as an important factor in the development of the industry and is mainly aimed at attracting women.

Promoting the employment of women and girls has identified information and communication technologies (ICT) as one of the sectors that can help create additional jobs for young people. Vacancies in the digital technology sector continue to grow. Increasing the level of computer literacy of women is one of the important grounds for our further development. Today, the main goal of

many young girls and our women is to increase activity in the process of social and economic reforms, embody high moral qualities, and form national thinking.

In short, a woman is a creator, a woman is a helper in everything. A woman who connects life to life, generation to generation. A woman is the trust and support of the family and society.

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